

FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF FLOATING TABLETS OF ALOGLIPTIN USING DIFFERENT POLYMERS

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Abstract:

The objective of this study was to develop and evaluate floating tablets of Alogliptin using different polymers, including Acacia, Carbopol 940, and Xanthan gum. Floating drug delivery systems are designed to prolong the gastric residence time, thus enhancing drug absorption. Various formulations of Alogliptin floating tablets were prepared using the aforementioned polymers, and their pre-compression and post-compression parameters, such as tablet hardness, weight variation, friability, and floating behavior, were evaluated. Among all the formulations, formulation A2, which contained a combination of Carbopol 940 and Xanthan gum, demonstrated the most promising results in terms of floating characteristics, drug release profile. A2 formulation showed an excellent drug release of 99.61% over 12 hours, compared to other formulations. This formulation also met the acceptable limits for pre-compression and post-compression parameters, indicating its potential for optimized therapeutic performance. Based on these findings, formulation A2 was considered the most suitable and optimized formulation for floating Alogliptin tablets, providing controlled release and improved therapeutic outcomes.

Keywords: Alogliptin Floating Tablets, Acacia, Carbopol 940, and Xanthan gum.

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1. INTRODUCTION:

The aim of drug delivery system is to afford a therapeutic amount of drug to the proper site in the body to attain promptly and then maintain desired drug concentration. The oral route is increasingly being used for the delivery of therapeutic agents because the low cost of the therapy and ease of administration lead to high levels of patient compliance. More than 50% of the drug delivery systems available in the market are oral drug delivery systems¹⁻⁴. Gastric emptying of dosage forms is an extremely variable process and ability to prolong and control the emptying time is a valuable

asset for dosage forms, which reside in the stomach for a longer period of time than conventional dosage forms. Several difficulties are faced in designing controlled release systems for better absorption and enhanced bioavailability. One of such difficulties is the inability to confine the dosage form in the desired area of the gastrointestinal tract. The relatively brief gastric emptying time (GET) in humans which normally averages 2-3 h through the major absorption zone, i.e., stomach and upper part of the intestine can result in incomplete drug release from the drug delivery system leading to reduced efficacy of the administered dose. Sustained releases

are dosage forms that provide medication over an extended period of time. Controlled release denotes that the system is able to provide some actual therapeutic control⁵. Controlled release (modified release) dosage forms are growing in popularity. These more sophisticated systems can be used as a means of altering the pharmacokinetic behavior of drugs in order to provide twice or once a day dosage. This is achieved by obtaining a zero-order release from the dosage form. Zero-order release includes drug release from the dosage form that is independent of the amount of drug in the delivery system⁶.

The controlled gastric retention of solid dosage forms may be achieved by the mechanisms of mucoadhesion, flotation, sedimentation, expansion, modified shape systems, or by the simultaneous administration of pharmacological agents, that delay gastric emptying. Oral controlled drug release dosage forms should not be developed unless the recommended dosage interval for the controlled release dosage form is longer than that for immediate release dosage form or unless significant clinical advantages for the controlled release dosage form can be justified like the decreased side effects resulting from a lower C_{max} with the controlled release Form as compared to the immediate release or conventional dosage form. In vivo/in vitro evaluation of FDDS has been discussed by scientists to assess the efficiency and application of such systems. Several recent examples have been reported showing the efficiency of such systems for drugs with bioavailability problems.^{7,8,9}

The concept of floating tablets is mainly based on the matrix type drug delivery system such that the drug remains embedded in the matrix which after coming in contact with the gastric fluid swells up and the slow erosion of the drug without disintegration of the tablet takes place. Sometimes for generating a floating system we even need to add some effervescent or gas generating agent which will also ultimately reduce the density of the system and serve the goal of achieving a floating system. These systems have a particular advantage that they can be retained in the stomach and assist in improving the oral sustained delivery of drugs that have an absorption window in a particular region of the GIT. These systems continuously release the drug before it reaches the absorption window, thus ensuring optimal bioavailability. Different approaches are currently used to prolong the gastric retention time, like hydro dynamically balanced systems, swelling and expanding systems, polymeric bio-adhesive systems, modified shape systems, high density systems and other delayed gastric emptying devices. The principle of buoyant preparation offers a simple and practical approach to achieve increased gastric residence time for the dosage form and sustained drug release¹⁰.

Advantages of FDDS

- ✓ FDDS is highly advantageous in the treatment of the disorders related to the stomach. As the prime objective of such systems is to produce a gastro retentive product or a product which has an enhanced retention time in the stomach⁸.
- ✓ Drugs with considerably short half life can be administered in this manner to get an appreciable therapeutic activity. Enhancement of the bioavailability for drugs which can be metabolized in the upper GIT.
- ✓ They also have an advantage over the conventional system as it can be used to overcome the adversities of gastric retention time as well as the gastric emptying time.
- ✓ The duration of treatment through a single dose, which releases the active ingredient over an extended period of time
- ✓ The active entity is delivered specifically to the site of action, thus minimizing or eliminating the side effects.

Disadvantages of FDDS:

- ✓ The major disadvantage of floating system is requirement of a sufficient high level of fluids in the stomach for the drug delivery to float. However this limitation can be overcome by coating the dosage form with the help of bioadhesive polymers that easily adhere to the mucosal lining of the stomach⁹
- ✓ Gastric retention is influenced by many factors such as gastric motility, pH and presence of food. These factors are never constant and hence the buoyancy cannot be predicted.
- ✓ Drugs that cause irritation and lesion to gastric mucosa are not suitable to be formulated as floating drug delivery systems.
- ✓ High variability in gastric emptying time due to its all (or) non-emptying process.
- ✓ Patients should not be dosed with floating forms just before going to bed.
- ✓ Floating system is not feasible for those drugs that have solubility (or) stability problem in gastric fluids.
- ✓ The dosage form should be administered with a minimum of glass full of water (200-250 ml).
- ✓ The drugs, which are absorbed throughout GIT, which under go first-pass metabolism (Nifedipine, Propranolol etc.), are not desirable candidate

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

LIST OF THE MATERIAL

Alogliptin Procured From Mylan Laboratories, Hyderabad, India. Provided by SURA LABS, Dilsukhnagar, Hyderabad.
 Acacia Degussa India Ltd. (Mumbai, India).
 Carbopol 940 Arvind Remedies Ltd, Tamil nadu, India.
 Xanthan gum Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India
 Citric acid Laser Chemicals, Ahmedabad, India.
 Sodium bicarbonate Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India
 Aerosil Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India
 Talc Apex Chemicals, Ahmedabad, India.

LIST OF EQUIPMENT

Weighing Balance Sartorius
 Tablet Compression Machine (Multi station) Lab Press Limited, India.
 Hardness tester Monsanto, Mumbai, India.
 Vernier callipers Mitutoyo, Japan.
 Roche Friabilator Labindia, Mumbai, India
 Dissolution Apparatus Labindia, Mumbai, India
 UV-Visible Spectrophotometer Labindia, Mumbai, India
 pH meter Labindia, Mumbai, India
 FT-IR Spectrophotometer Bruker, Germany

METHODOLOGY

7.1. Analytical method development:

a) Determination of absorption maxima:

A solution containing the concentration 10 µg/ mL drug was prepared in 0.1N HCL UV spectrum was taken using a double-beam UV/VIS

spectrophotometer. The solution was scanned in the range of 200 – 400 nm.

b) Preparation of calibration curve:

10mg Alogliptin pure drug was dissolved in 10ml of methanol (stock solution1) from stock solution 1ml of solution was taken and made up with 10ml of 0.1N HCL (100µg/ml). From this, 1ml was taken and made up with 10 ml of 0.1N HCL (10µg/ml). The above solution was subsequently diluted with 0.1N HCL to obtain a series of dilutions containing 5, 10, 15, 20, 25µg /ml of per ml of solution. The absorbance of the above dilutions was measured at 290 nm by using a UV-Spectrophotometer taking 0.1N HCL as blank. Then a graph was plotted by taking Concentration on the X-axis and Absorbance on the Y-axis, which gives a straight line. Linearity of the standard curve was assessed from the square of the correlation coefficient (R^2), which was determined by least-square linear regression analysis.

7.3. Formulation development of floating

Tablets:

Procedure for the direct compression method:

- 1) The drug and all other ingredients were individually passed through a sieve no ≠ 60.
- 2) All the ingredients were mixed thoroughly by triturating for up to 15 min.
- 3) The powder mixture was lubricated with talc.
- 4) The tablets were prepared by using the direct compression method with an 8mm punch.

FORMULATION OF TABLETS:

INGREDIENTS (MG)	FORMULATION CODE								
	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9
Alogliptin	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
Acacia	25	50	75	-	-	-	-	-	-
Carbopol 940	-	-	-	25	50	75	-	-	-
Xanthan gum	-	-	-	-	-	-	25	50	75
Citric acid	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
Sodium bicarbonate	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
Aerosil	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Talc	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Magnesium stearate	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Microcrystalline cellulose	147	122	97	147	122	97	147	122	97
Total weight	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250

Table 7.3: Formulation composition for floating tablets

All the quantities were in mg

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

8.1. Analytical Method

a. Determination of absorption maxima

The standard curve is based on spectrophotometry. The maximum absorption was observed at 290 nm.

b. Calibration curve

Graphs of Alogliptin were taken in 0.1N HCL (pH 1.2)

Table no 8.1: Observations for the graph of Alogliptin in 0.1N HCL

Conc. [$\mu\text{g/mL}$]	Abs
0	0
5	0.107
10	0.204
15	0.315
20	0.426
25	0.527

Fig 8.1: Standard graph of Alogliptin in 0.1N HCL

Standard graph of Alogliptin was plotted as per the procedure in experimental method, and its linearity is shown in Table 8.1 and Fig. 8.1. The standard graph of Alogliptin showed good linearity with R^2 of 0.997, which indicates that it obeys the “Beer-Lambert” law.

8.3. Preformulation parameters of powder blend:

Table 8.2: Pre-formulation parameters of the blend

Formulation Code	Angle of Repose	Bulk density (gm/mL)	Tapped density (gm/mL)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's Ratio
A1	27.8 \pm 0.99	0.48 \pm 0.01	0.59 \pm 0.04	18.6 \pm 1.11	1.22 \pm 0.06
A2	27.9 \pm 0.58	0.47 \pm 0.02	0.57 \pm 0.05	17.54 \pm 0.58	1.5 \pm 0.06
A3	28.8 \pm 0.68	0.35 \pm 0.02	0.43 \pm 0.07	18.6 \pm 0.34	1.22 \pm 0.05
A4	28.3 \pm 0.80	0.34 \pm 0.01	0.40 \pm 0.09	15.00 \pm 1.10	1.17 \pm 0.09
A5	28.6 \pm 0.70	0.31 \pm 0.04	0.40 \pm 0.03	22.05 \pm 0.80	1.24 \pm 1.1

A6	28.4±0.45	0.32±0.05	0.41±0.05	21.95±0.75	1.26±0.04
A7	27.8±0.45	0.33±0.03	0.45±0.04	21.42±1.13	1.27±0.05
A8	27.9±0.66	0.38±0.02	0.45±0.04	16.90±1.12	1.19±0.08
A9	28.6±0.59	0.37±0.01	0.44±0.04	15.90±1.14	1.18±0.02

The tablet powder blend was subjected to various pre-formulation parameters. The angle of repose values indicate that the powder blend has good flow properties. The bulk density of all the formulations was found to be in the range of 27.8±0.45 to 28.8±0.68 (gm/ml), showing that the powder has good flow properties. The tapped density of all the formulations was found to be in the range of 0.40±0.03 to 0.59±0.04, showing the powder has good flow properties. The compressibility index of

all the formulations was found to be below 17.04, which shows that the powder has good flow properties. All the formulations have shown the Hausner's ratio ranging between 1.5±0.06 to 1.27±0.05, indicating the powder has good flow properties.

8.4. Quality Control Parameters for tablets:

Tablet quality control tests, such as weight variation, hardness, friability, thickness, Drug content and drug release studies were performed for floating tablets.

8.3. In vitro quality control parameters

Formulation codes	Weight variation (mg)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%loss)	Thickness (mm)	Drug content (%)	Floating lag time (sec)	Total Floating Time(Hrs)
A1	249.38	3.57	0.46	2.38	99.47	57	12
A2	250.69	3.36	0.39	2.31	99.62	45	12
A3	248.22	3.52	0.42	2.46	97.14	51	12
A4	247.86	3.48	0.55	2.59	98.22	49	12
A5	251.17	3.43	0.51	2.55	97.59	63	12
A6	245.37	3.55	0.68	2.34	99.83	59	12
A7	249.98	3.42	0.57	2.47	98.17	73	12
A8	251.45	3.49	0.44	2.51	97.29	66	12
A9	249.62	3.39	0.62	2.44	98.73	71	12

All the parameters for tablets, such as weight variation, friability, hardness, thickness, and drug content, were found to be within limits.

Figure 8.2: Floating lag time (sec)

Figure 8.3: Total Floating Time (Hrs)

8.5. *In Vitro* Drug Release Studies;

Table no 8.4: Dissolution data of Floating Tablets

Time (hr)	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	15.31	19.96	17.52	21.63	18.49	26.43	15.73	18.29	26.94
2	21.26	23.21	25.93	28.84	22.76	31.04	19.92	23.91	28.28
3	27.74	37.43	38.75	34.24	26.65	34.98	27.04	29.26	38.78
4	36.98	45.11	41.28	49.28	35.04	39.09	34.76	37.15	47.37
5	45.65	52.68	48.65	51.13	38.85	46.18	39.21	44.68	54.78
6	49.48	59.72	55.21	67.71	42.01	57.88	52.47	55.89	63.13
7	57.74	68.41	64.92	74.99	53.76	59.43	58.56	63.62	69.21
8	63.53	76.62	69.67	79.61	58.52	68.15	64.85	69.23	78.85
9	69.13	79.89	76.29	85.05	66.23	78.65	72.75	75.51	82.73
10	74.85	84.92	88.72	89.27	75.51	83.94	76.96	84.43	89.12
11	77.12	93.24	91.36	94.13	81.25	89.02	82.63	88.59	93.25
12	83.81	99.61	96.97	97.91	91.44	95.51	88.42	92.22	97.11

Figure 8.4: Dissolution data of Alogliptin Floating tablets containing Acacia

Figure 8.5 Dissolution data of Alogliptin Floating tablets containing Carbopol 940

Figure 8.6 Dissolution data of Alogliptin Floating tablets containing Xanthan gum

Whereas the formulations prepared with Acacia were retarded the drug release in the

concentration of 50mg (A2 Formulation) showed required release pattern i.e., retarded the drug release up to 12 hours and showed maximum of 99.61% in 12 hours with good retardation.

Whereas the formulations prepared with Carbopol 940 were retarded the drug release in the concentration of 25mg (A4 Formulation) showed required release pattern i.e., retarded the drug release up to 12 hours and showed maximum of 97.91 % in 12 hours with good retardation.

Whereas the formulations prepared with Xanthan gum were retarded the drug release in the concentration of 75 mg (A9Formulation) showed required release pattern i.e., retarded the drug release up to 12 hours and showed maximum of 97.11% in 12 hours with good retardation.

Hence, from the above dissolution data, it was concluded that the A2 formulation was considered as the optimized formulation because good drug release (99.61%) in 12 hours.

Application of Release Rate Kinetics to Dissolution Data for Optimised Formulation:

Table no 8.5: Application kinetics for optimised formulation

CUMULATIVE (%) RELEASE Q	TIME (T)	ROOT (T)	LOG(%) RELEASE	LOG (T)	LOG (%) REMAIN	RELEASE RATE (CUMULATIVE % RELEASE / t)	1/CUM% RELEASE	PEPPAS log Q/100	% Drug Remaining	Q01/3	Qt1/3	Q01/3-Qt1/3
0	0	0			2.000				100	4.642	4.642	0.000
19.96	1	1.000	1.300	0.000	1.903	19.960	0.0501	-0.700	80.04	4.642	4.310	0.332
23.21	2	1.414	1.366	0.301	1.885	11.605	0.0431	-0.634	76.79	4.642	4.250	0.391
37.43	3	1.732	1.573	0.477	1.796	12.477	0.0267	-0.427	62.57	4.642	3.970	0.672
45.11	4	2.000	1.654	0.602	1.739	11.278	0.0222	-0.346	54.89	4.642	3.800	0.841
52.68	5	2.236	1.722	0.699	1.675	10.536	0.0190	-0.278	47.32	4.642	3.617	1.025
59.72	6	2.449	1.776	0.778	1.605	9.953	0.0167	-0.224	40.28	4.642	3.428	1.214
68.41	7	2.646	1.835	0.845	1.500	9.773	0.0146	-0.165	31.59	4.642	3.161	1.480
76.62	8	2.828	1.884	0.903	1.369	9.578	0.0131	-0.116	23.38	4.642	2.859	1.782
79.89	9	3.000	1.902	0.954	1.303	8.877	0.0125	-0.098	20.11	4.642	2.719	1.922
84.92	10	3.162	1.929	1.000	1.178	8.492	0.0118	-0.071	15.08	4.642	2.471	2.171
93.24	11	3.317	1.970	1.041	0.830	8.476	0.0107	-0.030	6.76	4.642	1.891	2.751
99.61	12	3.464	1.998	1.079	-0.409	8.301	0.0100	-0.002	0.39	4.642	0.731	3.911

Figure 8.7: Zero-order release kinetics

Figure no 8.8: Higuchi release kinetics

Fig 8.9: Kors Mayer Peppas release kinetics

Fig 8.10: First-order release kinetics

Optimised formulation A2 was kept for release kinetic studies. From the above graphs, it was evident that formulation A2 followed the Korsmeyer-Peppas release kinetics mechanism.

8.6. Drug–Excipient Compatibility Studies Fourier Transform-Infrared Spectroscopy:

Figure 8.11: FTIR Spectrum of pure drug

Figure 8.12 FTIR Spectrum of optimized formulation

There was no disappearance of any characteristic peaks in the FTIR spectrum of the drug and the polymers used. This shows that there is no chemical interaction between the drug and the polymers used. The presence of peaks at the expected range confirms that the materials taken for the study are genuine and there were no possible interactions.

Alogliptin is also present in the physical mixture, which indicates that there is no interaction between the drug and the polymers, which confirms the stability of the drug.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, the formulation development and evaluation of floating tablets of Alogliptin using various polymers, such as Acacia, Carbopol 940, and

Xanthan gum, demonstrated promising results. Among the different formulations, formulation A2 exhibited superior characteristics in terms of floating behavior, drug release profile. Incorporating the selected polymers contributed to the optimal formulation, with A2 being identified as the most effective and optimized formulation. This formulation showed significant potential for floating drug release, improved bioavailability, and enhanced therapeutic outcomes. Therefore, A2 can be considered the ideal formulation for the development of floating tablets of Alogliptin.

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